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BASIC STUDY ON PLANNING OF DESIGN STRATEGY FOR AN AIRLINE

CASE STUDY ON STAR FLYER INC.(SFJ)

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ABSTRACT

In this study, on the basis of a new airline service between Haneda Airport and Fukuoka Airport, questionnaire surveys were carried out toward college students regarded as one of the customers to obtain the impression of Star Flyer Inc. (SFJ) and three competitive companies (JAL, ANA, SKY) and the criteria for choice of the airline, and then a design strategy for SFJ in the future was examined by analyzing survey results. As for a design strategy for SFJ in the future, it is concluded that the current directionality should be maintained for "A Design for Tangibles" which reflects in the evaluation of Image. On the other hand, for "A Design for Intangibles" which reflects to evaluation of Experiential Value, it is demanded to develop and push better service that provides comfortable feeling, security and the sense of fulfillment.

Keywords: Airline, Image & Experiential Value, Design Strategy

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent times there have been many hot topics in the airline industry, including the re-internationalization of Haneda Airport and the introduction of low cost carriers to the market. Star Flyer Inc. (SFJ), a new airline established in Kitakyushu City, Fukuoka Prefecture as a result of the industry deregulations of the 1990s, is an airline that stresses its uniqueness through, for example, the dark-toned design of the interior and exterior of its planes (Fig. 1) and the original coffee blend

served during in-flight service. The company plans to begin its new Haneda–Fukuoka route in July 2011. SFJ operates flights to and from Fukuoka Airport, Fukuoka city. The Fukuoka metropolitan region and its satellite towns are one of the largest academic areas in Japan, with 19 colleges and universities located there, including our institution, Kyushu University.

This survey targeted college students, one of the target markets for SFJ's Fukuoka route, investigating their image of the airline as a basis for guiding its future design strategy.

We conducted the study proposed and agreed by Kyushu University Faculty of Design and SFJ.

<http://www.starflyer.jp/inboard/seat.html> (last access; April 25, 2011)

<http://www.starflyer.jp/inboard/airbus.html> (last access; April 25, 2011)

Figure 1. Interior and exterior of SFJ planes

2. SURVEY

2.1. PREPARATION OF RANKING TERMS

2.1.1. Image ranking

Ninety college students were presented with 180 adjectives used in surveys (Tamura, R., 1997, 2006) related to product and regional image, and asked them to select those words they considered appropriate for the ranking of images of an airline. Valid responses were received from 69 participants, and responses showed variations among the selected words. Among those words selected, the seventeen words listed in Table 1, including “refreshing,” “fast,” and “sophisticated,” were chosen by at least 35% of respondents. Because analogous and dependency relationships were noted, we selected from the students surveyed four graduate students specializing in the analysis of design surveys, who performed a pairwise comparison using a 5-rank scale (where 1 = high similarity and 5 = high dissimilarity) of every word pair between the seventeen words (${}_{17}C_2 = 136$ pairs) for Minimum Dimension Analysis (MDA). The results of analysis indicated that minimum expressible dimensionality was 2, and as shown in Figure 2 five groups and three independent words were found. From the words forming the groups, the following words were selected as best representing the airline’s image: “sophisticated,” “sharp,” “relaxed,” “refined,” and “progressive.” To those words, the three independent words, “dynamic,” “fast,” and “formal” were added to determine the eight words to be used in image evaluation.

2.1.2. Experiential value ranking

Twelve college students, six male and six female, were interviewed regarding lingering positive and negative impressions of the airline after utilization. Laddering of the results was used to examine participant value perception. Doing so resulted in 74 examples (3-9 per participant), and reduction of similar results allowed for classification of 42 cases into 18 types of positive results, and 32 cases into 19 types of negative results. Positive impressions related to values were classified into four categories: “peace of mind,” “excitement,” “specialness,” and “frugality.”

refreshing	fast	sophisticated	relaxed
gorgeous	graceful	progressive	elegant
modern	sharp	safe	speedy
mechanical	formal	smart	dynamic
refined			

Table 1. Selected adjectives

Figure 2. The result of MDA and selected eight image words

Negative impressions were classified into three categories: “discomfort,” “anxiety,” and “dissatisfaction.” Figures 3 and 4 show an organized view of these categories. The “anxiety” category from the negative impressions and the “peace of mind” category from the positive impressions are opposing concepts, and are taken as explanatory of the same value. “Discomfort” and “dissatisfaction” are negative categories and so not appropriate as values evaluations, and so were replaced with the positive values “comfort” and “satisfaction.” As a result of the above, the six types of experiential value listed in Table 2 were selected as evaluation terms: “I felt excited,” “I felt peace of mind,” “I felt special,” “I felt like I got a good deal,” “I felt comfortable,” and “I felt fulfilled.”

2.1.3. Airline selection ranking

To better understand the thought processes behind airline selection, we examined a previous journal

Figure 3. Integrated diagram (positive impressions)

Figure 4. Integrated diagram (negative impressions)

I felt special	I felt excited	I felt fulfilled	I felt peace of mind
I felt comfortable	I felt like I got a good deal		

Table 2. Six experiential value words

article (Akao, Y. et al., 1984) and surveys (Yahoo Value Insight, 2008, Recruit Co., Ltd., 2010, Chikyu no Arukikata, 2010) to collect items related to considerations taken when making such decisions. We collected 51 items during our review, resulting in eighteen categories of related items, as follows: "Attitude of airline employees in the airport," "Attitude of airline employees within the airplane," "Snacks and drink service within the airplane," "Materials and equipment within the airplane," "In-flight entertainment (audio programs, magazines,

1. Attitude of airline employees in the airport
2. Attitude of airline employees within the airplane
3. Snacks and drink service within the airplane
4. Materials and equipment within the airplane
5. In-flight entertainment (audio programs, magazines, etc.)
6. Information delivery and support in the event of mishaps such as cancelled flights and delays
7. Information delivery and support in the event of full flights and waiting lists
8. Types of flight routes
9. Number of flights on routes
10. Ease of understanding and using reservations system (reservation website)
11. Ease and smoothness of checkin procedures
12. Airfares
13. Discount rates of discount programs and ease of understanding
14. Mileage point benefits and ease of use
15. Whether I am a member of the airline's mileage program
16. Whether it is an airline that I often use or am used to
17. Whether it is an airline that I like
18. Corporate image of the airline

Table 3. Eighteen criteria for selecting an airline

etc.), "Information delivery and support in the event of mishaps such as cancelled flights and delays," "Information delivery and support in the event of full flights and waiting lists," "Types of flight routes," "Number of flights on routes," "Ease of understanding and using reservations system (reservation website)," "Ease and smoothness of checkin procedures," "Airfares," "Discount rates of discount programs and ease of understanding," "Mileage point benefits and ease of use," "Whether I am a member of the airline's mileage program," "Whether it is an airline that I often use or am used to," "Whether it is an airline that I like," and "Corporate image of the airline." These items are listed in Table 3, and were used as ranking criteria.

2.2. SELECTIONS OF AIRLINES FOR TARGET OF THE SURVEY

Four airlines with Haneda-Fukuoka routes were examined in the survey: Japan Airlines (JAL), All Nippon Airways (ANA), Skymark Airlines (SKY), and SFJ.

2.3. QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY

The questionnaire survey was performed using participants at an event, "Let's design wonderful skies-An investigation of SFJ branding and service design," held at Kyushu University Ohashi Satellite from Tuesday, July 27 through Sunday, August 1, 2010. The survey used a five-rank scale (agree = 5, do not agree = 1) regarding the eight selected image

ranking words, six selected experiential value words, and favorableness as pertaining to the four airline companies listed above, and a five-rank scale (not important = 1, important = 5) regarding the eighteen ranking criteria for selecting an airline.

A total of 86 responses were received, and responses from 66 university students (38 male, 28 female) were used in the following analysis.

3. COMPARISON OF IMPRESSIONS

3.1. ANALYSIS

Those responses that were complete for all ranking words pertaining to image and experiential value were selected as valid, for totals of 238 responses for image ranking (SFJ: 46, JAL: 64, ANA: 63, SKY: 65) and 241 responses for experiential value (SFJ: 46, JAL: 65, ANA: 64, SKY: 65). These responses were used as the basis for factor analysis (Table 4).

Response rates indicate that SFJ has a relatively low recognition rate, approximately 30% lower than that of the other three airlines examined in the survey.

3.2. INTERPRETATION OF FACTOR ANALYSIS

Factor analysis allowed for the isolation of two factors related to image ranking with intrinsic values greater than 1 (Table 5). Factor loading sizes were large for first factors related to high quality such as “elegant” and “refined,” as were factor loading sizes for second factors related to trendiness such as “sharp” and “progressive.”

Factor analysis allowed for the isolation of two factors related to experiential value ranking with intrinsic values greater than 1 (Table 6). Factor loading sizes were large for first factors related to comfort such as “feeling comfortable” and “feeling safe,” as were factor loading sizes for second factors related to specialness such as “feeling special” and “feeling excitement.”

3.3. COMPARISON OF SFJ AND COMPETITORS WITHIN THE FACTOR SPACE

3.3.1. Comparison based on image ranking

Figure 5 shows 90% probability ellipses and average response values for each of the four airlines by sex. Average values show that there is a slight difference between sexes in ranking for the second factor of

	Image			Experiential value		
	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
SFJ	46 (69.7)	26 (68.4)	20 (71.4)	46 (69.7)	26 (68.4)	20 (71.4)
JAL	64 (97.0)	37 (97.4)	27 (96.4)	65 (98.5)	38 (100.0)	27 (96.4)
ANA	63 (95.5)	37 (97.4)	26 (92.9)	64 (97.0)	38 (100.0)	26 (92.9)
SKY	65 (98.5)	37 (97.4)	28 (100.0)	65 (98.5)	37 (97.4)	28 (100.0)

Table 4. Responses (%)

		Factor 1	Factor 2
Quality	Sophisticated	0.850	0.214
	Refined	0.784	0.352
	Relaxed	0.771	0.133
	Formal	0.769	0.088
Trendiness	Sharp	0.421	0.664
	Progressive	0.283	0.628
	Fast	-0.080	0.565
	Dynamic	0.053	0.131
Intrinsic values		3.694	1.355
Contribution ratio (%)		46.175	16.942
Accumulative contribution ratio (%)		46.175	63.117

Table 5. Factor loads for image

		Factor 1	Factor 2
Comfort	I felt comfortable	0.798	0.280
	I felt peace of mind	0.768	0.168
	I felt fulfilled	0.719	0.392
	I felt like I got a good deal	-0.383	-0.134
Specialness	I felt special	0.251	0.817
	I felt excited	0.257	0.742
Intrinsic value		3.228	1.024
Contribution ratio (%)		53.806	17.065
Accumulative contribution ratio (%)		53.806	70.871

Table 6. Factor loads for experiential value

trendiness. Examining salient features of the four airlines, SFJ is positioned positively for both first and second factors, indicating a high ranking in terms of both quality and trendiness. Despite slight differences between sexes, ANA, too, is positioned positively for both factors, indicating a similar image trend to SFJ. Conversely, JAL is positioned near the origin for the first factor and negatively for the second factor, indicating a low ranking for trendiness. SKY shows second factor positioning near the origin and first factor positioning negatively, indicating a low ranking for quality.

3.3.2. Comparisons based on experiential value ranking

Figure 6 shows 90% probability ellipses and average response values for each of the four airlines by sex.

Figure 5. The scatter diagram for image

Figure 6. The scatter diagram for experiential value

The 90% probability ellipses indicate significant differences between the four airlines, with high variation between respondents. Average values show slight differences between sexes for the second factor specialness for SFJ, JAL, and SKY, and only for ANA for the first factor comfort. Examining salient features of the four airlines, SFJ is positioned near the origin for the first factor, but positively for the second factor, indicating a high ranking for specialness. ANA is positioned near the origin for the second factor, but

positively for the first factor, indicating a high ranking for comfort. JAL is positioned positively for the first factor, but negatively for the second factor, particularly for men, indicating a low ranking for specialness. SKY is positioned negatively for both first and second factors, indicating a low ranking for both comfort and specialness.

4. AIRLINE SELECTION

As shown in Figure 7, among criteria used when selecting an airline, "Airmiles" scored 4.66 points among male students and 4.82 points among female students, while "Discount rates of discount programs and ease of understanding" scored 4.05 points among male students and 4.11 points among female students, indicating that cost is an important criteria. When examining airline image, "Information delivery and support in the event of mishaps such as cancelled flights and delays" was ranked third at a similar 3.96 for female students, indicating that airline image is important. While the ranking is seventh place at 3.71 among male students, it was ranked highly after "Ease of understanding and using reservation system (reservation website)" and "Information delivery and support in the event of full flights and waiting lists," etc. Analysis of impressions related to favorableness towards the airlines is taken up in the sections below.

5. ESTABLISHMENT OF A DESIGN STRATEGY

5.1. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN IMPRESSION AND FAVORABLENESS

We performed multiple regression analysis on image and experiential value using two factors derived from each as independent variables, and favorableness as the dependent variable. As shown in Tables 8 and 9, both rankings showed low multiple correlation coefficients, and while conformity is not very good the positive positioning of both the first and second factors affect favorableness rankings, the first factor in particular.

5.2. ESTABLISHMENT OF DESIGN STRATEGY

Based on the results described above, we believe that the establishment of a design strategy for an airline should consider measures for positioning both

Figure 7. The result of criteria used when selecting an airline

image and experiential value rankings in the positive direction of the factor space.

In the case of SFJ, the first and second factors related to image are both positioned in the positive direction, but there remains a need to move the first factor related to experiential value in that direction as well. Furthermore, there is a need to stabilize and therefore reduce the scatter area of both rankings. Design related to tangible elements such as attention to airplane interior and exterior appearance, which have a strong effect on image rankings, should be maintained and pursued further. Design related to intangible elements such as support and other services that are important factors in airline selection, which have a strong effect on experiential value rankings, should be used along with the tangible elements described above to further develop and improve feelings of comfort, security, and fulfillment.

	R = 0.552	R ² = 0.305		
	partial regression coefficient	standard partial regression coefficient	t	p
(constant)	3.521		69.026	0.000
Factor 1	0.466	0.462	8.417	0.000
Factor 2	0.282	0.247	4.497	0.000

Table 8. Result of multiple regression analysis on image

	R = 0.598	R ² = 0.357		
	partial regression coefficient	standard partial regression coefficient	t	p
(constant)	3.533		72.227	0.000
Factor 1	0.560	0.532	10.108	0.000
Factor 2	0.220	0.204	3.876	0.000

Table 9. Result of multiple regression analysis on experiential value

6. CONCLUSIONS

This survey involved college students as one of the target markets to investigate an airline, a business that has seldom been the subject of design strategy research.

We found two factors related to airline image (“quality” and “trendiness”) and experiential value (“comfort” and “specialness”). We also found that airline image is one of the most important factors in selection of an airline for travel. We furthermore found that both the image and experiential value factors affect the positive directionality of favorableness, the first factor in particular. Topics for future studies include an increased number of student participants in the questionnaire survey, and inclusion of other consumer targets.

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